

Crystal structure reinvestigation of alpha-, beta- and gamma-In₂S₃

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Abstract

Semiconducting indium sulfide (In₂S₃) has recently attracted considerable attention as buffer material in the field of thin film photovoltaics. Compared to this growing interest, however, detailed characterisations of the crystal structure of this material are rather scarce and controversial. In order to close this gap, we have carried out an in-situ X-ray diffraction study at various temperatures using monochromatic synchrotron radiation. Dedicated, high temperature synthesized polycrystalline In₂S₃ material was used for that purpose. We found three modification of In₂S₃ in the temperature range between 300 K and 1300 K, with structural phase transitions at temperatures of 717 K and above 1049 K. By Rietveld refinement we extracted the crystal structure data and the temperature coefficients of the lattice constants for all three phases, including a high temperature trigonal γ -In₂S₃ modification.

1. Introduction

In_2S_3 is a widegap semiconductor with high photoconductive and photoluminescent properties, which makes it a promising material for optoelectronic applications (Shazley *et al.*, 1998). Most prominently, its potential application as a buffer layer in chalcopyrite solar cells has triggered an increased research effort in its fundamental materials properties (like e.g. crystal structure, optical properties, electronic bandstructure, etc.) as well as in deposition technology. The compatibility with various thin film deposition methods make it a versatile alternative to the commonly applied CdS buffer layer. Among the compatible deposition methods, atomic layer deposition (Naghavi *et al.*, 2003), the Ion Layer Gas Reaction (ILGAR) method (Saez-Araoz *et al.*, 2012), spray pyrolysis (John *et al.*, 2005), sputtering (Hariskos *et al.*, 2005) and evaporation (Strohm *et al.*, 2005) can be listed. The interested reader is referred here to the excellent review by Barreau (2009) on the role of In_2S_3 in the world of photovoltaics. Various reports on In_2S_3 buffer layers correlate deposition process parameters with crystallographic properties (Rao & Kumar, 2012), (Larina *et al.*, 2004), (Yoosuf & Jayaraj, 2005) and ultimately with final solar cell device parameters (Naghavi *et al.*, 2003), (Pistor *et al.*, 2009b).

For a correct interpretation of the crystallographic data, a comprehensive understanding of the relevant crystal structure modifications of In_2S_3 is mandatory. However, literature on the phases in the In-S system is ambiguous and contradictory. In view of the recent technological and scientific interest in In_2S_3 and the commonly drawn connection to its crystal structure properties in this contribution we therefore aim at a complete description of the crystal structure of the In_2S_3 system in the relevant temperature regime from room temperature up to 1300 K, close to the melting point at 1363 K (Diehl *et al.*, 1976). This will not only lead to high quality reference XRD files but also to the profound knowledge on the different modifications, which

might lead to a direct impact on the technological understanding in terms of e.g. material quality or diffusion parameters.

The first to describe the crystal structure of In_2S_3 were Hahn & Klingler (1949). They reported a cubic phase, which they called $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ and, for temperatures above 600 K a transition to a tetragonal spinel-like high temperature modification which they called $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$. They already stressed the similarity between both modifications and suggested an ordering of the In atoms to be the main difference between the two phases. Later studies revealed that the cubic phase is in fact the higher-temperature phase and the stoichiometric phase existent at room temperature is tetragonal. However, for sulfur-deficient In_2S_3 the temperature range for the cubic phase extends down to room temperature. So Hahn probably measured a sulfur-deficient cubic $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ at room temperature and called it the lower temperature modification and from here most confusion about the nomenclature arises.

While the majority of authors follow Hahn in their nomenclature resulting in an ordering of the phases from low to high temperature as $\beta - \alpha - \gamma$, some have relabeled the cubic and tetragonal phase with a resulting order of $\alpha - \beta - \gamma$. When reviewing the literature attention has therefore to be paid as depending on the author $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ may refer to the low-temperature, tetragonal phase or the cubic high temperature phase. Although $\alpha - \beta - \gamma$ would be the logical order, we will follow the majority in literature and assign $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ to the low-temperature, tetragonal phase.

There are some more and sometimes contradictory publications in literature on the crystal structure of the different In_2S_3 phases, of which the most relevant ones will be shortly introduced in the following. Gödecke & Schubert (1985) suggest a phase diagram in which for the In:S ratio of 2:3 three modifications ($\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$, $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ and $\gamma\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$) of indium sulphide exist in three different temperature regimes. King et al. determined the spacegroup of the tetragonal $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ as $I4_1/\text{amd}$ (space group

No. 141) and the lattice parameters to $a_0 = 7.61 \text{ \AA}$ and $c_0 = 32.24 \text{ \AA}$ using Weissenberg photographs (King, 1962). The spacegroup was later confirmed by Goodyear and Steigmann who stated the lattice parameters as $a_0 = 7.623$ and $c_0 = 32.36 \text{ \AA}$ (Goodyear & Steigmann, 1961), (Steigmann *et al.*, 1965). Hahn described the space group of the cubic α - In_2S_3 as $Fd\bar{3}m$, with a lattice parameter of 10.72 \AA (Hahn & Klingler, 1949). The high-temperature γ - In_2S_3 modification has not been characterized in detail yet since a quenching to room temperature conditions was not successful (Diehl *et al.*, 1976). However, Diehl *et al.* succeeded in synthesizing a modified γ - In_2S_3 phase with an additional 5 at. % of As or Sb stabilizing it at room temperature. For this modified trigonal γ - In_2S_3 they suggested a spacegroup of $P\bar{3}m1$ with lattice parameters a_0 between 3.806 \AA and 3.831 \AA and c_0 between 9.044 \AA and 9.049 \AA .

Multiple recent publications refer to the thin film application of In_2S_3 and cite X-ray diffraction (XRD) database information. An assignment to the tetragonal β - In_2S_3 is often made although the quality of the diffraction data for In_2S_3 is generally poor and does not allow for a definite distinction between the tetragonal β - In_2S_3 and the cubic α - In_2S_3 . A correct distinction between the two phases would however allow for a verification of the film stoichiometry, as the β - In_2S_3 only exists in a very small stoichiometry range (Gödecke & Schubert, 1985). It is the scope of this work to reinvestigate the In_2S_3 in view of these aspects and to present a clear and detailed description of its crystal structure over the complete relevant temperature range.

2. Results

2.1. Temperature-dependent X-ray diffraction

In_2S_3 powder was prepared from the elements via a high temperature route as described in section A.1. The mortared In_2S_3 powder was filled into quartz ampoules which were instantaneously evacuated and sealed. The X-ray diffractograms were recorded

in the temperature range from 304 K to 1322 K and details on the diffraction measurements can be found in section A.2. We find three distinct phases in this temperature regime with a sharp structural phase transition between the first two phases at a temperature of $717 \text{ K} \pm 5 \text{ K}$. This transition is characterized by the disappearance of several minor intensity diffraction peaks while the main diffraction peak positions and intensities remain approximately constant for both phases (see figures 1,2,3). A second, broader transition was observed in the temperature range between 1049 K and 1084 K. Here, all peaks of the $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ disappear and are replaced by the diffraction peaks of $\gamma\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ indicating a complete reordering of constituents of the crystal structure. A colorscale map of all diffractograms is depicted in figure 1. In this graph, color indicates the counts and the three temperature regimes corresponding to the three different groups of diffraction patterns can be well distinguished.

2.2. Rietveld refinement

We carried out Rietveld refinements of the three diffractograms recorded at the temperatures of 309 K, 749 K and 1099 K. The software Fullprof Suite (Version February 2008) was used for this purpose (Rodriguez-Carvajal, 2001). For all three cases we obtained a good agreement between measurement and simulation with R_B and χ^2_ν values below 3 % and 12, respectively. The three diffractograms, refinements and residues are displayed in figures 2 to 4. The obtained crystal structure parameters are listed in table 1 with more detailed data on the obtained figures of merit and atomic positions in section A.3. Finally, the XRD data measured at different temperatures have been processed in batch-mode to extract the temperature dependence of the relevant lattice parameters, as exemplarily shown in figure 5 for the lattice parameter a for the cubic $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ phase in the temperature range between 749 K and 1044 K. The data are well fitted with a linear fit function of $a(T) = 10.7480\text{\AA} + 0.0001121(2)\text{\AA}/\text{K}$. From the tem-

perature dependence of the lattice constants, we obtain the linear thermal expansion coefficient α ($\alpha_T = (da/dT)_T/a_T$, (Kundra & Ali, 1976)) for the cubic phase. In this temperature range, we calculate an average α of $10.3 * 10^{-6}/K$, in relatively good agreement with reference (Kundra & Ali, 1976) ($10.8 * 10^{-6}$ - $10.9 * 10^{-6}/K$). The temperature dependence of the remaining lattice parameters of the tetragonal and trigonal phases are obtained accordingly and the fit functions summarized in table 2. For the tetragonal β - In_2S_3 we find an average linear expansion coefficient α in a-direction of $11.7 * 10^{-6}/K$, for the trigonal phase $14.1 * 10^{-6}/K$ in a-direction and $26.7 * 10^{-6}/K$ in c-direction. The determination of the lattice parameter c for the tetragonal phase showed two narrow inhomogeneities ranges around 484 K and 609 K, with large errors and negative expansion coefficients, whose origin is most probably due to problems in the refinement of the diffractograms at these temperatures. Excluding these regions, the average thermal expansion coefficient of the tetragonal phase in c-direction was determined to $6.7 * 10^{-6}/K$.

3. Discussion

In this section we will briefly discuss the crystal structure of the three modifications and how the different modifications may impact the application of In_2S_3 in thin film solar cells.

The low-temperature modification β - In_2S_3 is best described with a defect spinel-type structure. The sulphur atoms form a cubic closed-spaced sublattice, in which the In atoms occupy the tetrahedral and octahedral interstitials the same way cations do in a regular spinel like MgAl_2O_4 (Kleber *et al.*, 2002). While all the octahedral cation sites are occupied in the In_2S_3 , 1/3 of the tetrahedral sites remain unoccupied. For that reason the In_2S_3 structure is sometimes described in a quasi-ternary compound formula: $[\text{In}_{2/3}(\text{Vac})_{1/3}]^{\text{tet}}[\text{In}]_2^{\text{oct}}\text{S}_4$, where $[\]^{\text{tet}}$ and $[\]^{\text{oct}}$ denote tetrahedral and octa-

hedral sites and (*Vac*) the vacancies. In β - In_2S_3 , the vacancies are ordered along a 4_1 screw axis parallel to the c-axis. The ordering of the vacancies gives rise to a small distortion of the cubic symmetry of the regular spinel structure. This small distortion is the origin of the tetragonal structure of the β - In_2S_3 with lower symmetry and leads to the additional peaks observed in the X-ray diffraction. Figure 6 shows a schematic model of the β - In_2S_3 crystal structure in accordance with the results obtained by the Rietveld refinement.

The transition from the β - In_2S_3 to the α - In_2S_3 is an order-disorder transition. In α - In_2S_3 , the indium vacancies are randomly distributed over all tetrahedral sites, in contrast to the ordered fashion in the β - In_2S_3 . As a result of the disordering, α - In_2S_3 adopts a cubic crystal structure. The resulting higher crystal symmetry explains the observed disappearance of some of the minor intensity peaks in the diffractograms after the transition from β - In_2S_3 to α - In_2S_3 at 717 K.

Finally, the γ - In_2S_3 can be described as a layered structure as suggested by Diehl *et al.* and Bartzokas *et al.* (Diehl *et al.*, 1976), (Bartzokas *et al.*, 1978). Here, the S atoms remain in a nearly closed-packed sublattice while the indium atoms are exclusively found on octahedral sites forming a layered structure of subsequent S-In-S-In-S slabs.

The defect spinel-type structure of the β - In_2S_3 and α - In_2S_3 has a direct phenomenological and technological impact. Because of the great number of natural vacancies in the structure, In_2S_3 can host various other atoms such as Na or Cu within its original lattice configuration (Barreau *et al.*, 2006). Both have been found to diffuse efficiently through In_2S_3 thin films (Pistor *et al.*, 2009*a*), (Juma *et al.*, 2012*b*), (Juma *et al.*, 2012*a*). The diffusion phenomena at interfaces in thin film solar cells containing In_2S_3 have not yet been fully understood but might benefit from an in-depth knowledge of the crystal (vacancy) structure of In_2S_3 . Where XRD data of good quality exist, it is an easy task to distinguish between the tetragonal and cubic phase

of In_2S_3 by an examination of the characteristic additional peaks only present for the $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$. The differentiation between $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ and $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ allows to test for stoichiometry, since the tetragonal phase only exists in a very small compositional range. According to Gödecke & Schubert (1985) and Diehl & Nitsche (1975), the compositional range for the $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ is less than 1 at. %. Addition of a very small amount of surplus indium effectively suppresses the ordering of the In vacancies and therefore the formation of the tetragonal $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ phase. As a consequence, the crystal structure of off-stoichiometric $\text{In}_{2+x}\text{S}_3$ remains in the cubic $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ modification down to room temperature. This specific feature is used for example to check if In_2S_3 source material for an evaporation process is still within the described stoichiometry range (Pistor *et al.*, 2009b). Alike the distinction of polycrystalline powder material, this type of analysis tool would be rather desirable for the evaluation of In_2S_3 thin film material as well. However reasonable X-ray diffraction data are necessary to distinguish between the two very similar spectra in order to resolve the fine additional peaks, a criteria often not met for XRD pattern available on In_2S_3 thin films.

4. Conclusions

We provide a detailed crystal structure analysis of In_2S_3 over the entire temperature range from room temperature up to the melting point covering the three modifications $\beta\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$, $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ and $\gamma\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$. With this, we contribute to the comprehensive understanding of the different phases existent and their interdependence. The high-temperature phase $\gamma\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$ has been analysed and refined for the first time in the pure phase. Finally we show how the detailed knowledge of the phase diagram and the different In_2S_3 modifications might have a direct impact on the technological use of In_2S_3 in applications such as buffer layer deposition in thin film solar cell production.

Appendix A Experimental methods

A.1. Sample preparation

Indium sulphide was synthesized by heating weighted stoichiometric amounts of sulphur and indium in evacuated quartz ampoules. Source materials were indium granulate (>99.999% purity) and sulphur flakes (>99.999% purity). An excess of 4 atomic percent of S was provided for two reasons: a) To account for sulphur losses during the preparation. b) The excess sulphur is not incorporated into the crystal structure according to the phase diagram (Gödecke & Schubert, 1985). The weighted source materials were placed in a graphite boat and placed in a quartz glass ampoule, evacuated ($< 10^{-3}$ mbar) and sealed. The ampoule was placed in a two-zone oven and heated above 1373 K for 24 h to enable the complete sulfurisation of the indium and to melt the built indium sulphide. To assure that the complete phase transitions could place, the ampoule was then kept at 1073 K for 2 days, at 873 K for 2 days and at 673 K for 4 days. The synthesized indium sulphide was manually ground in a mortar before XRD measurements and had a brick red appearance.

A.2. Diffraction measurement

For the diffraction measurement, ground indium sulphide powder was sealed in an quartz ampoule. The XRD measurements were performed at the ESRF, the European Synchrotron, Grenoble, France at the beamline ID15B using monochromatic high energy synchrotron light with a wavelength of 0.14276 Å. XRD patterns were recorded every 5 K while heating the sample from 304 K to 1322 K with a constant heating rate of 300 K / h.

A.3. Refinement and crystal structure details

In this section the details of the refinement and crystal structure parameters will be displayed. Table 3 lists the obtained Rietveld refinement parameters for the three Rietveld refinements carried out. Table 1 gives an overview of the general structure parameters of the three analysed phases, while in Table 4 to Table 6 the atomic sites for each phase and refinement can be found.

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Table 1. *Lattice parameters as extracted from the Rietveld refinement for the three In₂S₃ modifications.*

		Temp.	Space group	Number	a ₀ = b ₀	c ₀	α = β	γ
#1	β-In ₂ S ₃	309 K	I4 ₁ /amd	141	7.6231(4) Å	32.358(4) Å	90°	90°
#2	α-In ₂ S ₃	749 K	Fd3̄m	241	10.8315(2) Å	10.8315(2) Å	90°	90°
#3	γ-In ₂ S ₃	1099 K	P3̄m1	164	3.8656(2) Å	9.1569(5) Å	90°	120°

Table 2. *Linear fit function of the lattice parameters of In₂S₃ from the Rietveld refinements.*

		Temp. range	Fit function
#1	β-In ₂ S ₃	309 K - 704 K	$a = 7.5949(2)\text{Å} + 8.967(31) T \times 10^{-5} \text{Å/K}$ $c = 32.307(2)\text{Å} + 1.607(4) T \times 10^{-4} \text{Å/K}$
#2	α-In ₂ S ₃	749 K - 1044 K	$a = 10.7480(2)\text{Å} + 1.121(2) T \times 10^{-4} \text{Å/K}$
#3	γ-In ₂ S ₃	1099 K - 1322 K	$a = 3.8044(2)\text{Å} + 5.566(15) T \times 10^{-5} \text{Å/K}$ $c = 8.877(3)\text{Å} + 2.52(2) T \times 10^{-4} \text{Å/K}$

Table 3. *Refinement parameters for the Rietveld refinements performed for the three modifications of In₂S₃. R_B: Bragg-R_I-Factor, χ_ν²: χ_ν² for points with Bragg contribution, R_{wp}: weighted profile R-factor (not corrected for background), R_{exp}: expected R-factor (not corrected for background), cR_{wp}: weighted profile R-factor (corrected for background), cR_{exp}: expected R-factor (corrected for background), Ratio_{h/p}: ratio between number of reflections and parameters.*

		Temp. (K)	χ _ν ²	R _B (%)	R _{wp} (%)	R _{exp} (%)	cR _{wp} (%)	cR _{exp} (%)	Ratio _{h/p}
#1	β-In ₂ S ₃	309 K	10.4	1.38	3.1	1.0	4.9	1.5	5.1
#2	α-In ₂ S ₃	749 K	7.9	1.69	2.8	1.0	5.5	2.0	7.3
#3	γ-In ₂ S ₃	1099 K	11.4	2.86	3.0	1.0	7.1	2.3	3.1

Table 4. *Atomic sites for the tetragonal β -In₂S₃.*

Atom	Wickoff	x	y	z	occ.	Biso
In1	8e	0	1/4	0.2046(2)	7.8	0.8
In2	8c	0	0	0	7.8	1.1
In3	16h	0	-0.0196(3)	0.3327(2)	15.6	0.9
S1	16h	0	-0.0053(22)	0.2513(7)	16	1.0
S2	16h	0	0.0081(21)	0.0775(8)	16	1.2
S3	16h	0	0.0204(20)	0.4133(8)	16	1.2

Table 5. *Atomic sites for the cubic α -In₂S₃.*

Atom	Wickoff	x	y	z	occ.	Biso
In1	8a	1/8	1/8	1/8	5.1	2.4
In2	16d	1/2	1/2	1/2	15.6	3.5
S1	32e	0.2564(2)	0.2564(2)	0.2564(2)	32.0	2.7

Table 6. *Atomic sites for the trigonal γ -In₂S₃.*

Atom	Wickoff	x	y	z	occ.	Biso
In1	2d	1/3	2/3	0.8079(4)	0.75	4.0
In2	2d	1/3	2/3	0.6485(15)	0.14	6.2
S1	2d	1/3	2/3	0.3357(8)	0.93	4.3
S2	1a	0	0	0	0.50	8.8

Fig. 1. Map of temperature-dependent X-ray diffractograms (XRD) for the In_2S_3 powder. Each diffractogram is measured at a specific temperature which corresponds to one column in the graph with the y-direction displaying the 2Θ diffraction angle. The position of the column in x-direction corresponds to the temperature at which the diffractogram was recorded, while the colour indicates the XRD intensity in logarithmic scale (dark blue = low intensity, red = high intensity). Three structural modifications of In_2S_3 in different temperature regimes can be distinguished according to appearing/disappearing diffraction peaks as indicated in the figure. Wavelength of the incident X-ray photons: 0.14276 Å.

Fig. 2. Diffraction data and Rietveld refinement for In_2S_3 powder in the tetragonal modification at a temperature of 309 K. The displayed residuum has been vertically shifted for better comparison.

Fig. 3. Diffraction data and Rietveld refinement for In_2S_3 powder in the cubic modification at a temperature of 749 K. The displayed residuum has been vertically shifted for better comparison.

Fig. 4. Diffraction data and Rietveld refinement for In_2S_3 powder in the trigonal modification at a temperature of 1099 K. The displayed residuum has been vertically shifted for better comparison.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of the lattice parameter for the cubic $\alpha\text{-In}_2\text{S}_3$. The resulting fit parameters of a linear fit are listed in the inset.

Fig. 6. Structure model of an β - In_2S_3 unit cell. The tetrahedral bonds are drawn thicker for better identification. The indium vacancies are marked as grey spheres. In the tetragonal β - In_2S_3 configuration, the vacancies are ordered on a 4_1 screw axis parallel to the c -axis of the crystal. In the α - In_2S_3 configuration, the vacancies are randomly distributed over all tetrahedral indium sites. The edges of the unit cell of the corresponding cubic α - In_2S_3 structure are indicated as blue lines.

Synopsis

We report on high resolution structure analysis of In_2S_3 powder with monochromatic synchrotron light in the temperature range between 300K and 1300K. Three modifications could be identified with the two phase transitions taken place at 717 K and above 1049 K. Crystal structure parameters and their temperature dependence for all three phases are extracted from the diffraction data by Rietveld refinement.
